

THE IMPACT OF PORTFOLIO WRITING ON IRANIAN EFL LEARNERS' AUTONOMY

Zahra Jafari, Kermanshah Science and Research Branch, Islamic Azad University, Iran
jafarizahra57@yahoo.com

Hamid Gholami, Department of Foreign Language Studies, Kermanshah Branch,
Islamic Azad University, Kermanshah, Iran.
Hamid_gholami7@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

The study investigated the impact of portfolio writing (European Language Portfolio) on learner autonomy on Iranian EFL students. Sixty elementary EFL learners, who were both male and female studying English at some language schools in Kermanshah, Iran were selected. They were divided into two groups. In the experimental group, European Language Portfolio was used while the control group underwent the traditional assessment and didn't receive any treatment. Learner Autonomy Questionnaire (LAQ) was used as the measure of learners' autonomy. Nine dimensions of LAQ were analyzed separately by using t-test. The findings suggest that learners' autonomy increases as the effect of portfolio writing. The results indicate that practicing portfolio writing can enhance learner autonomy in general and in most of the dimensions.

KEY WORDS: Learner Autonomy, Language portfolio, European Language Portfolio (ELP)

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the concept of autonomous learning was introduced into the field of education in 1950's, a wide research has been made in this field. Linguistic scholars began their study on autonomous learning in 1970's, gradually it was accepted that another goal in language learning is to cultivate students' ability of autonomous learning. And these researches reflected the transition of teaching emphasis from teacher-centered to students-centered learning (Zhuang, 2010). According to Demirtaş and Sert (2010) the essence of the learner-centered approach is the learner-autonomy.

Dickinson (1987) exposed that autonomy refer to the situation in which learners are totally responsible for all of the decisions concerned with learning and the implementation of those decisions. Therefore one of the main challenges that educational system faced is how to help learners move toward becoming responsible for their own learning. In traditional system of language learning in Iran students are passive learners and there is no opportunity for them to enhance their learning autonomy. Learners' self-assessment and alternative assessment is one area of learner autonomy. Among different kinds of assessment, portfolio writing and actually

European Language Portfolio (ELP) is of a great importance. Thus the main purpose of this study is to find out the impact of European Language Portfolio (ELP) on learner autonomy of the beginner EFL learner.

2. Review of the Literature

Interest in the autonomy of the individual probably dates back to the time of Aristotle and has influenced political developments in the 20th century which have had a major impact on education (Lamb & Reinders, 2005). The definition of the term autonomy, however, has been controversial. Holec (1981) was the first person to define the learner autonomy as "the ability to take charge of one's learning"(p. 3). Littlewood (1996) defined autonomy as "learners' ability and willingness to make choices independently"(p. 97). Kohonen (2002) stated that to be able to take charge of their learning and to extend their skills students need to be actively involved in the whole learning process, so they need to prepare for increasingly international communicative settings and situations in the modern world. Whatever the definition, there have been proposed a lot of different techniques to improve autonomy, self assessment techniques can be considered as some examples of which.

A portfolio is a purposeful collection of student work that exhibits the student's effort, progress, and achievements in one or more areas and this collection must include student participation in selecting contents, the criteria for selection, the criteria for judging merit, and evidence of student self-reflection (Paulson, Paulson, & Meyer, 1991). According to Richard (1998) the primary value of portfolios is in the assessment of student achievement, because they provide a continuous record of students' language development that can be shared with other students. For Crosby (1997) the primary purpose of portfolios in EFL context is to increase the level of students' motivation and to give them a sense autonomous learning. Lee (2001) argued that portfolio assessment prioritized student-centered over conventional concept of teaching.

The European Language Portfolio (ELP) is part of the Council of Europe's Common European Framework for Language Teaching (CEF 2001), which based on recent outcome of a long-term commitment to promote the learning and teaching of modern languages in Europe, The work consistently has emphasis on a broad learner-centered basic orientation in language teaching (Kohonen, 2002).

According to council of Europe (2004) the European Language Portfolio includes information on learner's language proficiency and experiences with the target language. While compiling their most important written and spoken tasks, e.g. recordings, videos and texts, that learners can follow their progress in language learning process. An essential part of the portfolio work is self-assessment and reflection which help learners to achieve a deeper understanding of their learning process. The language portfolio describes learner's language skills on the Common European Framework of Reference scale. The European Language Portfolio includes information about learners' language proficiency, learners compile their language portfolio during the course of the studies (Council of Europe, 2004). The ELP is a document in which those who are learning or have learned a language - whether at

school or outside school- can record and reflect on their language learning and cultural experience.

According to the Council of Europe (2004) ELP has three obligatory parts consisting of

- a) Language Passport: regularly updated by users, it shows what the student can do in different languages and incorporates a self-assessment, grid for reference purposes that describes the competences in the different skills (speaking, reading, listening and writing) and helps users in their reflection and self-assessment. It is also contains information about diplomas, courses and contacts with other languages and cultures.
- b) Language Biography: where users describe their experiences in any of the languages they are learning. It is designed to guide learners to plan and evaluate their learning progress. This is the most innovative part, providing the tools to control the learning process as a whole.
- c) Dossier: contains the evidences, i.e. samples of personal work to illustrate their language command. Users add certificates, diplomas, written work, projects, audio, video recordings presentations, etc.

3. Research question and hypothesis

The question that is aimed to be answered in general considering the a aforementioned points in this study was

Does portfolio writing improve Iranian EFL learners' autonomy?

Based on the research question mentioned above, the following hypotheses emerge: Portfolio writing doesn't improve Iranian EFL learners' autonomy.

4. Methodology

The subjects participating in the research were all Iranian students, both male and female studying English in Kermanshah, Iran. They were all beginners. 60 elementary level students were selected. Language Autonomy Questionnaire (LAQ) was administered to the all 60 students. Out of this number of student, 30 participants were selected for experimental group and 30 participants were selected for control group. This sample population provided the main data for this experiment the treatment.

To gather data, Learner Autonomy Questionnaire (LAQ) was administered to investigate the extent to which learners are autonomous. The LAQ was basically formed by Egel in 2003, but Gholami and Biria (2013) changed some parts of the questionnaire in their study. In the study the same questionnaire as used by Gholami and Biria (2013) was administered. They reported the reliability of the questionnaire about .74 by using the Cronbach Alpha. LAQ includes nine dimensions, and the items of LAQ dimensions demonstrated whether learners display a greater degree of control in particular aspects of their learning. Table 1 below displays the nine dimensions of autonomy in the questionnaire.

Table1 Nine Dimensions of Autonomy the Learner Autonomy Questionnaire

Section	Number of items	Focus	Questions
Dimension 1	6 items	Readiness for Self-direction	What are the learners' beliefs relating to self-directed learning in general?
Dimension 2	6 items	Independent Work in Language Learning	What are the learners' beliefs relating to independent work in language learning?
Dimension 3	8 items	Importance of Class/Teacher	How important do learners see the class/ the teacher in their language learning?
Dimension 4	5 items	Role of Teacher: Explanation/Supervision	What importance do learners give to teacher explanation and supervision?
Dimension 5	4 items	Language Learning Activities Outside the Class	In relation to particular language learning activities, what are the learners' attitudes?
Dimension 6	3 items	Selection of Content	What are the learners' attitudes relating to the selection of content for language learning?
Dimension 7	3 items	Intrinsic motivation	How confident do learners feel about defining objectives?
Dimension 8	5 items	Assessment/ Motivation	How important is external assessment in motivating the learners' work?
Dimension 9	4 items	Interest in the Target Cultures	What are the learners' attitudes relating to the culture of other countries?

Gholami and Biria (2013)

In LAQ the Likert scale was employed by asking the participants to respond to all of the 44 statements by indicating whether each statement is "always true", "mostly true", "sometimes true", "rarely true", and "never true" for themselves. The items in the LAQ were based on independency and dependency; therefore a reverse scoring system was necessary for the independent items in order to discriminate between attitudes of autonomous learners and those of non-autonomous learners.

To collect the data, the LAQ was administered in class with a twenty -minute allotted time as a pre-test and after the implementation period at the end of the semester and after twenty three sessions as a post-test.

In the first part of ELP, language Passport, the students filled blanks and wrote the date of getting command of any goal. In the next part they ticked the grid (table) corresponding their ability. The grid contained some information in four skills (reading, writing, speaking and listening) in three levels A1 (breakthrough), A2 (waystage) and A3 (threshold), that the students ticked them with its date.

In the second part of ELP, Language Biography, the students filled in the blanks about four skills in different topics such as, the local and wider community, people and places in other countries, animals and plants, then wrote its date. This part contained different levels (A1, A2, and A3). In the next part they wrote the date of activities that they can do. For instance " I can understand the words for people who help us ". In each session the students wrote the date of those activities that they can do.

In the third part of ELP named dossier, the students keep examples of the work they have done, pictures they have drawn, and lists of new words. They can use the dossier to show their teachers and parents what they have learned.

When the treatment carried out, and the experimental group has done their activities on ELP, ALQ was administered to both experimental group and control group as a post -test to investigate impact of ELP on learner autonomy.

5. Data Analysis

After administering the questionnaire as the pretest, the results were analyzed using independent t-test to determine any significant difference between the groups in terms of autonomy level. In all of the LAQ statistical data analyses, probability level was set to .05 ($\alpha < .05$). As indicated in table 2, there is no significant difference between the groups ($0.916 > .05$).

Table: 2 Statistics for ALQ as a pretest

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	df	sig(2-tailed)
Dg-Cnt	30	120.90	8.80	.106	58	0.916
Dg-Exp	30	121.17	10.59			

The nine dimensions in LAQ were also examined respectively in order to see the differences between control group posttest and experimental group posttest scores on each dimension. Based on *independent sample t-test* results in Table 3 for dimension 1, the mean in the control group posttest is 19.56 and in experimental group post-test scores is 22.13, differences between mean scores of the two groups was found to be significant ($t(58) = 2.45, p < 0.05$). The *sig* (.017<.05) depicts that there is an increase in the extent the students are ready to participate in self-directed activities when learning English after the implementation period. So it can be considered that the students have adapted to their new role in the language learning process. The second dimension,

Independent Work in Language Learning, includes of seven items which cover the students' general attitudes to independent learning. Therefore these items investigated if the students are able to learn English on their own without the presence of a teacher. The increase of mean score in the experimental group and ($t(58) = 1.52, p < 0.05$), *p-value* (.013<.05) illustrated that there is an increase in the students' tendencies towards the aspect of independency in their foreign language learning processes after the treatment span.

Dimension 3: Importance of Class/ Teacher aimed to discover the students' evaluation of the importance of the classroom setting in learning English and the English teacher's role. The dimension consists of eight items. Five of these items are based on the attitudes of non-autonomous learners' feelings that the teacher plays a very important role in learning a foreign language, but the other three items are on the basis of learner independency. For which, reverse scoring was conducted. In this dimension, the higher score that the student get, the less important they regard the classroom and the teacher .As shown in Table 3, although the mean score in the experimental group increased but ($t(58) = 1.78$) and the sig (.079 >.05) indicates no difference between the groups. Therefore it can conclude that ELP didn't improve learner autonomy in this dimension. The fourth Dimension, Role of Teacher: Explanation/ Supervision, contained five items all of which dealt with the learner's dependency on the teacher. In this dimension the increase in the mean score of the experimental group and ($t(58) = 3.10, p < 0.05$) and the p-value (.003 <.05) indicate that students have become less dependent on the teacher. Therefore, it can be inferred that the role of the teacher has become less and less important for the students as the study progressed

Table 3 Statistics for The impact of multidimensional approach on dimensions of

Dimensions		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
D1	Cnt	30	19.56	4.12	2.45	58	.017
	Exp	30	22.13	3.98			
D2	Cnt	30	20.33	6.18	1.52	58	.013
	Exp	30	22.93	6.97			
D3	Cnt	30	22.06	5.40	1.78	58	.079
	Exp	30	24.96	7.50			
D4	Cnt	30	15.36	3.88	3.10	58	.003
	Exp	30	18.33	3.51			
D5	Cnt	30	11.20	3.80	1.57	58	.876
	Exp	30	11.36	4.42			
D6	Cnt	30	8.06	2.61	1.19	58	.236

learner autonomy

	Exp	30	9.13	4.11			
D7	Cnt	30	6.86	1.45	4.04	58	.000
	Exp	30	8.56	1.81			
D8	Cnt	30	14.20	8.84	2.53	58	.014
	Exp	30	16.53	4.15			
D9	Cnt	30	10.30	3.90	2.99	58	.004
	Exp	30	13.66	4.77			

As table 3 indicates, the mean scores of control group is 11.20 and in experimental group 11.36 in Dimension 5: Language Learning Activities. The *sig* (.876>.05) indicates that the student were less willing to do the classroom activities outside the classroom. In the sixth dimension: Selection of Content, which is based on the students' tendency toward sharing the responsibility for selecting the content and materials for their English lesson, the mean score of the control group posttest is 8.60 and in experimental group post-test is 9.13. In this dimension, based on the *sig* (.237>.05), it can be concluded that the portfolio writing didn't effect on learners' autonomy in choosing of the content.

Dimension 7: Objectives/ Evaluation , involved three items which attempted to investigate the students' intrinsic motivation for language learning, the mean score of the control group is 6.86 and in experimental group post-test is 8.56. In this dimension, (t (58) = 4.04, p < 0.05) and the *sig* (.003 <.05) indicates that learners feel more confident about setting objectives for themselves, and accordingly this enhances their intrinsic motivation.

Dimension 8 , Assessment/ Motivation, attempted to find out students' attitudes toward external assessment and its role in motivating the students' work. The increase in mean scores of the experimental group rather than control group and (t (58) = 2.53, p < 0.05) and the *sig* (.014 <.05) indicates the effectiveness of ELP on learner autonomy in this dimension, therefore, external assessment become less important in motivating the learners' work. Dimension 9, Other Cultures, investigate the learners' attitudes toward the culture of other countries. As table 3 shows that, the mean score of the control group posttest in dimension 9 is 10.30 and the mean score of the experimental group posttest is 13.66. In this dimension (t (58) = 2.99, p < 0.05) and the *sig* (.004 <.05) shows the meaningful increase in the experimental group on the post- test.

Another t-test was run to see if portfolio writing can improve learner autonomy in general. The result showed that the experimental group had higher scores rather than control group, which may referred a stronger orientation toward autonomy after the twenty-three session implementation span. Table 4.13 indicates the statistically significant (.012<.05) difference between the mean values of the control group posttest score and experimental group posttest scores of LAQ.

Table 4 General Statistics for ALQ as a posttest.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	df	Sig(2-tailed)
Dg-Cnt	30	128.73	14.48	2.58	58	.012
Dg-Exp	30	141.00	21.60			

6. Conclusion

The current research tries to investigate a way to improve learner autonomy in an Asian context which is assumed to be a teacher-centered one. European Language Portfolio was practiced as a way to develop learner autonomy. The results indicate that, European Language Portfolio can enhance learner autonomy in general and in all dimensions except dimensions three, five and six. The fact that it develops some of the dimensions and not all, calls for a more comprehensive approach to develop autonomy

REFERENCES

- Chan, V. (2001). Readiness for learner autonomy: What do our learners tell us?. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 6(4), 505-518.
- Council of Europe, (2004): European Language Portfolio (ELP): Principles and Guidelines. *With added explanatory notes*. Strasbourg: Council of Europe.
- Crosby, C. (1997). Portfolio assessment in the Korean ESL writing classroom. *Thai TESOL Bulletin*, 10(2).
- Demirtaş, İ., & Sert, N. (2010). English education at university level: Who is at the centre of the learning process. *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*, 4(2), 159-172.
- Dickinson, L. (1987). *Self-Instruction in Language Learning*. Cambridge. Cambridge University Press
- Gardner, D. (2000). Self-assessment for autonomous language learners. *Links & Letters*, 7.
- Gholami, H., & Biria, R. (2013). Explicit Strategy Training and Learner Autonomy. *Journal of Basic and Applied Scientific Research*, 3(5)1048-1052
- Göksu, A., & Genç, B. (2011). The Contribution of the European Language Portfolio to Autonomy in Reading Skills. *Edited by David Gardner*.
- Holec, H. (1981). *Autonomy in foreign language learning*. Oxford: Program Press.
- Kohonen, V. (2002). The European language portfolio: from portfolio assessment to portfolio-oriented language learning. *Quo vadis foreign language education*, 77-95.
- Lamb, T. E., & Reinders, H. (2005). Learner independence in language teaching: A concept of change. *An international perspective on language policies, practices and proficiencies*, 225-239.
- Lee, K. C. (2001). Teaching materials and methods of comprehensive activity fields. *Taipei: Shin-Lee*.

- Little wood, W. (1996). "Autonomy": an anatomy and a framework. *System*, 24(4), 427-435.
- Neupane, M. (2010). Learner autonomy: concept and considerations. *Journal of NELTA*, 15(1-2), 114-120.
- Paulson, F. L., Paulson, P. R., & Meyer, C. A. (1991). What makes a portfolio a portfolio. *Educational leadership*, 48(5)
- Zhuang, J. (2010). The Changing Role of Teachers in the Development of Learner Autonomy—Based on a Survey of "English Dorm Activity". *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 1(5), 591-595.